

About the Nature of M-S Bond in Complex Compounds

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COMPLEX formation can be interpreted as an acid base reaction, in which the metal acts as an acid and the ligand as a base. A linear relationship between the stability of the complexes of a metal ion and the base dissociation constants of the corresponding ligands, has also been shown¹. This relationship should hold good in case of structurally related ligands. Literature² reveals that non-transition metals form more stable complexes with the ligands containing elements in the second period of a group as the coordinating atoms, whereas the ligands involving later elements of the group form less stable complexes. The reverse is, however, observed in case of transition metals. The relative stabilities of the complexes containing nitrogen, phosphorus and arsenic atoms have been worked out by Nyholm and coworkers³. Coates⁴ observed that the strength of coordination of $X(\text{Me})_3$ ($X=\text{O}, \text{S}, \text{Se}$ or Te) to aluminium trimethyl is in the order of $\text{O} > \text{S} > \text{Se} > \text{Te}$, but the dialkyl sulphides and tellurides coordinate with Pd(II), Pt(II) and Hg(II) whereas others do not, indicating reverse order of stability ($\text{S} > \text{O}$). In the transition metal complexes Pettit and coworkers⁵ observed that the silver complexes of phenylselenoacetic acid is more stable than the corresponding sulphur and oxygen analogues. There is, however, no uniform pattern of relative coordinating affinities of all ligand atoms for all acceptor molecules and ions, not even when only simple unidentate ligands of closely analogous structures (e. g. $\text{PR}_3, \text{R}_2\text{S}$) are considered. The relative affinities seem to depend more on the acceptors concerned. It was observed that under comparable conditions the relative tendencies of the alkyls of the fifth and sixth group atoms to coordinate with trimethyl gallium are $\text{N} > \text{P} > \text{As} > \text{Sb}$ and $\text{O} > \text{S} > \text{Se} > \text{Te}$ but the order appears to be $\text{N} < \text{P} > \text{As} > \text{Sb}$ and $\text{O} < \text{S} > \text{Se} > \text{Te}$ towards Pt(II). Other similar divergent examples have been observed.

In spite of this lack of uniformity some regular features have emerged⁶:

- (i) There is generally a difference between the co-ordinating affinities of the first and the second element from each of the three groups of ligand atom in periodic table i. e. between nitrogen and phosphorus, oxygen and sulphur and fluorine and chlorine.
- (ii) There are two classes of acceptors:

- (A) those which form their stable complexes with the first ligand of each group i.e. with nitrogen and fluorine, and
- (B) those which form their most stable complexes with the second or subsequent ligand atoms.

Class A consists of most metals in their common valency states. The tendency of the ligands to get bound with such acceptors is directly dependent on their basicities, except in the cases where steric and other factor bring interference. The acceptors of class B, are less in number and are situated in an area of more or less triangular shape in the central part of the periodic table.

Pearson⁷, on the basis of his independent observations, grouped the metals and ligands as hard and soft Lewis acids and bases, respectively. He observed that the hard acids have a greater tendency to combine with hard bases and vice versa. Pearson's hard and soft acids correspond to metals with A and B character and hard and soft bases correspond to ligands containing earlier and later elements of a group, respectively.

In view of the quantum mechanical concept of coordination, the class A or class B character of the metal ions is connected with the availability of d electrons and the electronegativity of the metal ion and π -bond formation.

An interpretation of π bonding has also been attempted in terms of molecular orbital theory. In normal mode of overlap, the T_{2g} orbitals of the metal ion do not find orbitals of the required symmetry on the ligand atom and hence remain as non-bonding molecular orbitals. In cases where the ligands have vacant $p\pi$ or $d\pi$ atomic orbitals on the ligand atom or the ligand molecules have vacant antibonding π molecular orbitals, they combine to form composite orbitals of the required symmetry to combine with the metal π orbital. π bonding and π antibonding molecular orbitals are thus formed. In terms of ligand field theory, the formation of π bonding and π -antibonding molecular orbitals increases the ligand field splitting, consequently increasing the stability of the complex.

Except in special cases (e.g. NO_2^- , 2,2'-dipyridyl, pyridine, CN^- , CO complexes where M-O or M-N $d\pi-p\pi$ interaction can take place)⁸, oxygen and

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nitrogen have no π orbitals available to accept the electrons from the suitably placed d orbitals on the metal atoms. On the other hand sulphur and phosphorus have vacant d orbitals which can be used for d π -p π bonding. Such π bonding is possible only with transition metals having electrons in d π orbitals. The conditions are most favourable with later transition metals in their normal oxidation states. Thus, for these metal ion complexes the stability increases in the order

The extent to which such M $\rightarrow$ L π bonding occurs is difficult to assess, but the available evidence suggests that in favourable circumstances it does occur in the M-L bond in transition metal complexes with ligands containing phosphorous, arsenic and to a lesser extent in sulphur, selenium and tellurium containing ligands⁹. Nyholm and coworkers⁹ observed greater stability of phosphine and arsine complexes compared to ammonia and explained it on the basis of the π interaction in M-P and M-As bonds.

Jorgensen¹⁰ pointed out that soft base behaviour of sulphur containing ligands may not be due to the M $\rightarrow$ L π back bonding but may be due to polarization of sulphur by the metal ion. He has interpreted this in terms of charge transfer into continuum orbitals of the ligand. According to Klopman¹¹, in case of heteronuclear compounds with large difference in energies of the outermost orbitals of the reactants, very little electron transfer occurs and the interaction is ionic. However, if the difference in the energies of the interacting orbitals is small, covalent bond formation takes place. The interaction of class B metals and soft base ligands, like sulphur containing ones belongs to the latter type while the bonding of class A metals with hard base ligands containing oxygen atoms are of the former type. The covalent interaction will definitely make the M-S bond stronger in case of class B type of metals.

Unfortunately ligands having sulphur, selenium and tellurium have been less extensively studied, although in recent years there has been considerable interest shown in sulphur containing ligands¹²⁻¹⁸. The stability constant of the complexes of several sulphur containing ligands have been measured. The stability constants of the metal complexes of thioglycollic acid, β -mercapto propionic acid, 2-amino ethane thiol and mercapto succinic acid have been determined¹⁹. Stabilities of uranyl chelates of hydroxy, mercapto and amino derivatives of acetic, propionic and salicylic acids fall in the order NH₂ > OH > SH. Uranyl ion forms a stronger complex with glycollate than with thioglycollate ion²⁰. This indicates class A behaviour of uranyl ion. Formation constants of the complexes of thioglycollic acid, thiolactic acid, thiosalicylic acid and their oxygen analogues with Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Mn(II) and Tl(I) have been studied²¹⁻²⁴. We have

also carried out the study of complexes with O and S containing anilides and acids and have shown that M-S interaction is stronger than M-O²⁵⁻²⁶. Allen and coworkers²⁷ have observed weak class B character of rhenium(II). Both Mn(II) and Re(II) are border line cases. Martin²⁸ also observed that the formation constants of mercapto acetamide complexes of Ni(II) and Mn(II) are in the order of Ni > Mn.

The stronger binding of sulphur with class B type of metal ions is of importance in biochemical processes. Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ have a high affinity for sulphur or nonheme iron sulphur proteins²⁹. The first row transition metal ions are known to coordinate to cystine through NH₂ and S and carboxylate remains unco-ordinated³⁰. Similarly penicillamide, -SC-CH₂-CH(NH₂) COO⁻, also co-ordinates to transition metal ions through -NH₂ and S³¹.

Gerlach and Holm³² have carried out nmr studies of the β -amino thione and the corresponding oxygen compounds and indicated π interaction in the Ni-S bond. ESR studies of copper diethyl dithiocarbamate complex also indicated presence of Cu-S π bond³³. Possibility of M $\rightarrow$ L π interaction has also been discussed in a recent review article by Pettit⁹. Nanjo and coworkers obtained the nmr spectrum of Ni(EtOCSS⁻)₂ complex and observed shift in the ligand protons indicating that the unpaired electrons of Ni(II) are partially delocalized on the system of the ligand. Richards and Johnson³⁴ have also shown the possibility of M $\rightarrow$ S π interaction on the basis of Mossbauer studies on dicyano-1,2-dithioethylene complex of Fe(III). The high magnitude of the isomer shift has been interpreted presumably as a consequence of the electron donation from the ligand orbitals to the metal d π orbitals with little contribution from back donation from metal orbital into empty ligand π orbitals. Bonamico and Dessy³⁵ carried out X-ray studies of complexes involving M-S and M-Se bonds and observed M-L bond distance to be shorter than a single bond. This indicates the formation of M $\rightarrow$ L π bonds. Further structural studies showing double bond character in M-S bond in solid complexes of class B metals are essential to finally establish the existence of π interaction.

References

1. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILLIAM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
2. I. GRENTHE, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1962, 16, 1965.
3. A. KABESH and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 3245.
4. G. E. COATES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 2003.
5. L. D. PETTIT, C. S. SHERRINGTON and R. J. WHEWELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 2204.
6. S. AHLAND, J. CHATT and N. DAVIES, *Quart. Review*, 1958, 12, 165.
7. R. G. PEARSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 3533.
8. S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Quart. Review*, 1965, 19, 386.
9. L. D. PETTIT, *Quart. Review*, 1971, 25, 130.
10. C. K. JORGENSEN, *Structure and Bonding*, 1967, 3, 106.
11. G. KLOPMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 223.

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12. H. L. NIGAM, R. C. KAPOOR, UMA KAPOOR and S. C. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 447.
13. H. L. NIGAM and S. C. SINHA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 117.
14. R. S. SAXENA, K. C. GUPTA and M. L. MITTAL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, 30, 189.
15. A. W. KUMAR and H. L. NIGAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, 4, 472.
16. R. S. SAXENA, K. C. GUPTA and M. L. MITTAL, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1968, 21, 641.
17. M. CEFOLA, A. S. TOMPA, A. V. CELIANO and P. S. GENTILE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 290.
18. V. L. WANGER and J. H. YOE, *Talanta*, 1959, 1, 223.
19. L. G. SILLEN and A. E. MARTELL, *Chem. Soc., London*, Special Publ. No. 17, 1964.
20. M. CEFOLA, R. C. TAYLOR, P. S. GENTILE and A. V. CELIANI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 790.
21. M. V. REDDY and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 282.
22. M. V. REDDY and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 1058.
23. M. V. REDDY and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Prakt. Chemie.*, 1970, 312, 69.
24. M. V. REDDY and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, 32, 232.
25. K. P. APTE, Ph.D. Thesis, 1972, Vikram University.
26. SAFALA NAMJOSHI, Ph.D. Thesis, 1973, Vikram University.
27. E. A. ALLEN, N. P. JOHNSON, D. T. ROSEVEAR and W. WILKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 788.
28. D. R. MARTIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 1076.
29. T. G. SPIRO and P. SALTMAN, *Structure and Bonding*, 1969, 6, 116.
30. D. D. PERRIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 290.
31. D. D. PERRIN and F. C. SAYCEE, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1968, 53.
32. D. H. GERLACH and R. H. HOLM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 91, 3457.
33. S. E. HARRISON and J. M. ASSOW, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, 40, 465.
34. R. RICHARDS and C. J. E. JOHNSON, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1971, 799.
35. M. BONAMICO and G. DESSEY, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1971, 264.